

Some Doublethiol Derivatives Containing Antimony and Alkali Metals

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A series of doublethiol derivatives $MSb(SBu^t)_4$ (where $M=Li, Na$ or K) containing trivalent antimony and alkali metal has been isolated. The derivative containing lithium was found to be monomeric in boiling chloroform and the other two are found to be insoluble in common organic solvents.

IN comparison to metal—oxygen—carbon bonded metal alkoxides^{1,2} $M(OR)_n$, the thiol derivatives $M(SR)_n$, having metal—sulphur—carbon bonds^{3,4,5,6} are of comparative recent interest. A good number of metal alkoxides have been found to be polymeric^{1,2}. This is mainly due to the capability of alkoxy groups to act as a bridge between two metal atoms, which also help the central metal atoms to achieve higher co-ordinated state as well. Recently a good number of double alkoxides $MM'(OR)_{n+n'}$, have been isolated and studied, in which two different metals M and M' having valencies of n and n' respectively have been linked together with the aid of alkoxy bridges⁷.

In view of the above, analogous doublethiol derivatives⁸ containing two different metals have been isolated during the course of the present investigations⁶.

Results and Discussion

The attempt to isolate the doublethiol derivatives $MSb(SR)_4$ by the addition of alkali metals M to alkylthioantimonites $Sb(SR)_3$ ⁴, dissolved in the medium of the excess of the primary R^*SH or secondary thiols R^*SH , did not lead to any successful result probably due to the dominating reducing property of these primary and secondary thiols along with the liberated hydrogen.

In view of the comparative stability of $Sb(SBu^t)_3$ ^{4,6} with respect to other alkylthioantimonites $Sb(SR)_3$ ^{4,6} derived from various primary and secondary thiols, towards air and moisture⁴ (probably due to the poorer reducing nature of tert-butane thiol⁶) doublethiol derivatives have been isolated from the tert-butanethioantimonite $Sb(SBu^t)_3$ ^{4,6} only. The derivatives have been isolated by the reaction of alkali mercaptides with tert-butylthioantimonites in the medium of tertiary

butane thiol and a little amount of dry methanol :

where $M=Li, Na$ or K .

The results have been summarised in table 1.

The light yellow coloured solid compound containing lithium $LiSb(SBu^t)_4$ was found to be monomeric ebullioscopically in boiling chloroform, whereas the other two derivatives $NaSb(SBu^t)_4$ and $KSb(SBu^t)_4$ were found to be white solids and almost insoluble in parent thiol and all other common organic solvents. However, the greater covalent character of a number of lithium compounds in comparison to those of sodium and potassium is pretty well known. Moreover the entity of these two isolated derivatives was also confirmed by their insoluble nature, as the starting thioantimonite $Sb(SBu^t)_3$ ^{4,6}, from which these doublethiol derivatives have been isolated is soluble in parent thiol, benzene and all other common organic solvents. It is tempting to include here that the four co-ordinated state of alkali metals⁹ is well-established alongwith the cationic chemistry of trivalent antimony as antimonite ion $[SbX_4]^-$ in a good number of compounds containing antimony⁹.

Experimental

In order to estimate antimony(III) in the doublethiol derivatives $MSb(SBu^t)_4$, a known quantity of the compound was digested with iodine solution in the medium of hot, dilute hydrochloric acid. After removing the excess of iodine by boiling and making the medium alkaline with the aid of sodium bicarbonate, antimony(III) was estimated iodimetrically¹⁰. The tert-butylthio groups were estimated iodimetrically¹¹ after dissolving the compounds in the medium of dilute hydrochloric acid.

TABLE I—PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF THE DOUBLETHIOL DERIVATIVES OF THE TYPE $MSb(SBu^t)_4$ (Where M=Li, Na or K)

	Wt. of the alkali metal taken. (g)	Wt. of $Sb(SBu^t)_3$ added (g) in the molar ratio 1 : 1	Amount of parent thiol (Bu^tSH) added (ml.)	Yield (g)	Analysis				For. wt. and the nature of the product.	Determined Mol. wt.
					Calcd. Sb(%)	($-SBu^t$) gr.	Found Sb(%)	($-SBu^t$) gr.		
1	Lithium 0.539	3.0264 (1 mole)	80 ml.	Calcd. 3.77 g. obtd. 3.57 g.	25.0	73.5	25.7	74.5	Calcd. as $LiSb(SBu^t)_4$ is 485 light yellow coloured solid	423, 476 504, 433 455, 448 481, 446 in boiling chloroform
2	Sodium 0.1419	2.4934 (1 mole)	80 ml.	Calcd. 3.1 g. obtd. 3.1 g.	24.27	71.11	23.61	71.37	$NaSb(SBu^t)_4$ 501 white solid.	insoluble in common organic solvents.
3	Potassium 0.331	3.2165 (1 mole)	80 ml.	Calcd. 4.39 g. obtd. 4.13 g.	23.54	68.90	24.01	69.48	$KSb(SBu^t)_4$ 517 white solid.	insoluble in common organic solvents.

A weighed amount of the alkali metal was allowed to dissolve in tert-butane thiol alongwith the gradual addition of dry methanol; as the reactivity of alkali metals towards pure and rigorously dry tertiary butane-thiol was found to be very poor. The alkali tert-butyl mercaptide, thus prepared, was mixed with the required amount of tert-butylthioantimonite⁴ in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 and was refluxed in the presence of excess of tert-butane thiol. The solid double thiol derivative was isolated by removing the excess of thiol first by distillation under atmospheric pressure followed by the removal of the remaining traces of solvent in vacuo. The results are summarised in table 1.

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